

ARTICULATORY AND ACOUSTIC PHONETIC PATTERNS IN PHILIPPINE CLASSROOM DISCOURSE: A LINGUISTIC INVESTIGATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15813717>

ABSTRACT

This study examined and explored the use of spoken English as a lingua franca (ELF) by students in oral communication courses at a university in Manila, where English is increasingly used as a medium of instruction. English serves as a lingua franca for individuals with diverse first languages in this context. The current study analyzed students' proficiency in pronunciation in this context and how the use of spoken lingua franca English demonstrates non-native-like phonetics, employing the Descriptive Analysis design. The primary objective was to identify the specific elements of pronunciation that lead to breakdowns in communication. The content consists of six hours of unedited digital recordings capturing students' organically occurring, genuine high-stakes talk. The results indicate a distinct inclination among students to engage in non-standard pronunciation features and prioritize functionality, hence discarding traditional forms. There seems to be a communication breakdown due to the frequent use of non-standard forms. This discourse will build upon the findings of this inquiry.

Keywords: *Phonemes, Phonetics, Phonological Error, Phonemics*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippines is home to eighty-five million Filipinos. Given the country's archipelagic nature, comprising 7,000 islands, it is no wonder that the Philippines has a

diverse range of languages. According to Paul Lewis's (2009) study in *Ethnologue: Languages of the World*, the Philippines has 175 listed individual languages. Of these, 171 are living languages, and the other four have no known speakers. This is not to mention that immigrants in the country use several languages. These include American, Spanish, Japanese, Chinese, and, most recently, Korean due to their choice of studying English here.

This situation confuses students, especially in the English classroom, when learning speech communication, as this subject entails correct pronunciation, enunciation, and diction. Having acquired the regional language, it seems to have a unique way of pronouncing words. Usually, if you are from the north, it is expected that your pronunciation is a little "harder" than that of those living in Central Luzon, which is a region where speaking the English language is highly concentrated, especially in schools and more often in people's daily conversations. Students from the provinces usually face challenges in adjusting to or learning in the speech class, primarily due to their difficulty in producing sounds using the English language. It is not the English language that they find challenging to learn, but rather the pronunciation of it.

Using phonetic transcription in the classroom, particularly in the Philippine classroom, has several drawbacks, as researchers have experienced in their many years of teaching it. The most significant of these is that it requires both teachers and students to be familiar with the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA). Atkielski (2005) noted that the IPA is easy to learn—despite the daunting appearance it might have at first—because there is an exact one-to-one correspondence between written symbols and spoken sounds. Additionally, according to him, many students have already encountered the IPA during their early schooling, such as in high school. Many dictionaries use the IPA, so anyone who has made any significant use of a dictionary has probably seen the IPA, even if he has not fully memorized the entire alphabet.

The ability to speak adequately becomes a valuable factor for advancement in any chosen career, especially nowadays, where stiff competition among recent graduates is very prevalent. The focus on teaching speech was prompted by the researchers' growing awareness of the learners' need to communicate effectively in this rapidly evolving, competitive, and industrialized society. The researchers are also teachers who have observed that the deficiency in students' speaking ability, particularly in pronunciation, has not received special attention from those who they think should be responsible—the English department and the teachers of speaking, respectively. This coincides with the study by Amelhay and Sakale (2024), titled "Importance of Listening and Speaking in English Language Acquisition," which argues that listening and speaking are often overlooked in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classroom, despite being essential for language fluency. The authors emphasize that students develop better language accuracy and confidence when given meaningful, interactive speaking tasks. They advocate for a more communicative and student-centered approach to language teaching. Therefore, students today must be equipped with a strong command of spoken English. Besides, young people nowadays often prefer to work overseas; in such cases, the use of global English seems to be of great value.

On the other hand, many students and teachers struggle to understand the concepts of IPA and transcription when they are first introduced to them. It is crucial to elucidate the benefits of transcription to them, thereby raising their awareness of its utility. As educators, the researchers ensure that, at the start of the talk, they emphasize the importance of mastering phonetics for accurate word pronunciation, particularly during the transcription process. Mastering the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA) offers significant benefits, as it enables individuals to comprehend and produce accurate phonetic transcriptions. These rewards outweigh the time investment needed to master the alphabet. According to Atkielski (2005), the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA) can be applied to any language without requiring additional learning, as it is not restricted to English alone. She emphasizes that even languages like Chinese, which are significantly different from English, can be transcribed using the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA).

The absence of phonemic awareness appears to be a significant barrier to achieving accurate pronunciation. Students who cannot divide words and syllables into phonemes face difficulties in accurately determining the correct sound of a word. As a result, individuals with pronunciation problems cannot effectively articulate certain letters, such as th, f, and v, as well as the set of vowel sounds. This ability to accurately produce sounds is a defining trait of individuals with pronunciation disabilities. The individual appears to be experiencing difficulties in producing speech sounds and positioning the speech organs appropriately. Certain students in the intermediate level of the speaking class, aged 16–19, experience significant pronunciation challenges that hinder their ability to participate fully in oral presentations within the class. These issues are typically not inherent and cannot be immediately rectified; however, with suitable programs, activities, and training, they can be mitigated without proper intervention. The students' pronunciation problems may require a focused emphasis on speech correction techniques to improve their ability to create the sound patterns of words accurately. An intervention program can be devised and executed to enhance pupils' awareness of pronunciation, thereby correcting speech errors. Therefore, the most dependable measure of a speech impairment is the capacity to articulate a single word. Similarly, a study conducted by Lousada et al. (2014) demonstrated that a structured phonological intervention program significantly improved the pronunciation and speech intelligibility of preschool children with speech sound disorders. The most notable gains were observed through single-word articulation tasks, which proved to be more sensitive in detecting improvements than measures of connected speech. This supports the use of single-word articulation as a dependable tool for identifying and tracking speech impairments (Lousada et al., 2014).

In this regard, the researchers aim to develop the students' speech communication skills by providing a lesson centered on learning the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA), with a focus on articulating consonants and, in particular, vowels. A review of the present syllabus in purposeful communication reveals a strong focus on lectures about communication and types of speeches, without merely discussing the technical aspects of speech elements, particularly pronunciation. The syllabus focuses more on the use of various speeches or the teaching of IPA (because only a few hours are allotted to teaching it), which the researcher thinks should also receive focus. This is also true of the findings

of Breitzkreutz et al. (2002), who noted that many ESL teachers lack formal training in pronunciation instruction, despite being equipped to teach public speaking elements such as delivery, stage presence, and managing anxiety. As a result, pronunciation—arguably the most critical aspect of speech for intelligibility—is often neglected in classroom practice. This supports prior observation that while English professors may teach various components of speech, they tend to overlook focused instruction on pronunciation (Breitzkreutz et al., 2002). The researchers believe that a good speaker should also deliver correct utterances of words, not only in terms of how the speaker presents himself on the platform, but also through proper gesturing and maintaining a proper posture. As noted by the researchers, based on analysis of previous records and personal observation in their classes, the syllabus they are using helps students feel that they have covered all the essential points of the subject. However, when speaking tests are administered, with an explicit focus on correct pronunciation or enunciation, students appear weak. The researchers' constant interaction with the students has allowed them to identify their pronunciation deficiencies.

Moreover, the researchers observed from the numerous speech classes they handled that most students have problems with articulation. Many tend to make incorrect word choices that conflict with the meaning they intend to convey as speakers. These wrong utterances are best manifested in the articulation of the consonants, specifically the “th” and “v”, better known as the fricatives. Although students may also have difficulty articulating other consonants and vowels, the researchers would like to focus on defective consonants and vowels that students find most challenging to articulate. This inability to speak correctly is merely a result of limiting the student's ability to learn phonetics. These observations and views provide the reason for this study. The writers of this paper believe teachers must be concerned with the teaching of phonetics. To improve students' pronunciation, the writers propose a lesson segment focusing on the articulation of consonants and vowels. Thus, Doronilla (1995) suggests that a more complex form of syllabus would be appropriate, incorporating several categories, including structures and communicative functions, as well as topic areas and recommended target activities. Richards (2001) supports Doronilla's (1995) call for a more complex syllabus by emphasizing the effectiveness of integrating multiple strands into course design. He argues that a well-rounded syllabus should not only include grammatical structures but also communicative functions, situational or topical content, and task-based activities that reflect real-life communication. This multi-stranded approach ensures learners gain both linguistic competence and communicative ability in meaningful contexts. Like Doronilla's proposal, Richards highlights that combining these elements leads to more effective and relevant language instruction (Richards, 2001; Doronilla, 1995).

Research Questions

The objective of this study was to rectify the pronunciation inaccuracies exhibited by second-year college students enrolled in a speaking class. The results of this study will provide a foundation for incorporating or maintaining the use of IPA in the curriculum of purposeful communication courses to enhance speaking proficiency.

More precisely, the study aimed to address the following inquiries:

1. What are the prevalent pronunciation errors that students frequently make when speaking?
2. What exercises can be devised for speech correction?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a qualitative design, specifically descriptive analysis, to identify the non-standard phonological characteristics common among the participants. The study participants consist of college students who are currently enrolled in Purposive Communication classes during the first semester of the academic year. Approximately 145 students were divided into four divisions and had their remarks digitally recorded. The number of students was reduced from 145 to just 20. The group of 20 students consisted of individuals who displayed non-standard phonological characteristics, as outlined by Kirkpatrick in his study on pedagogical implications. The 20 selected official participants who met the inclusion criterion were chosen using a Purposive sampling design. Upon meticulous examination and observation of the recorded films, the researchers analyzed the multilingual model and the lingua franca method. The researchers employed a reading task using a selected excerpt from a manuscript, specifically a presidential speech that emphasizes clear pronunciation as a characteristic of this type of speech. This task was used to evaluate the participants' capability to produce speech and assess their familiarity with the words. The researchers utilized a standardized speech excerpt that was authorized and provided to each participant for reading into to collect the data. The researchers carefully examined and verified the segment of the performance that aligns with the descriptions based on the participants' verbal output through thematic analysis. The performance of the composition is being recorded on video. The collected data were observed and examined. The researchers identified the common non-standard phonological characteristics among the participants by conducting a frequency analysis using the non-standard phonological features table provided by Kirkpatrick (2010) for ASEAN English Language Learners (ELF) users. Kirkpatrick argues that if a typical cognitivist framework for second language acquisition (SLA) insists on adopting either a British or American model, then all the traits are categorized as mistakes. The sound patterns exhibiting a significant number of errors were deemed non-standard phonological characteristics of the participants. The data were deliberated and examined based on the ELF table below.

Table 1: Summary of Pronunciation Features Shared by ELF Users

Student number	Non-standard phonological features								
	Reduction of consonant clusters	Dental fricatives	Vowel merging	Mono-phthongization	Reduced initial aspiration	Bisyllabic triphthongs	Lack of reduced vowels	Stressed pronouns	Heavy end-stress
1	6	4	11	7	2	6	9	6	5
2	33	48	56	51	32	41	55	28	18
3	5	4	9	3	2	3	11	6	5
4	23	40	31	12	21	34	42	19	16
5	15	9	21	11	6	4	18	11	16
6	6	21	21	4	8	8	18	6	3
7	18	18	38	13	11	9	31	14	19
8	21	18	30	18	21	18	26	18	15
9	18	26	38	12	11	18	27	12	23
10	21	28	36	27	21	18	33	15	29
11	16	4	12	5	9	11	16	4	11
12	18	14	19	16	4	8	15	12	11
13	15	6	21	17	5	16	16	7	16
14	20	16	31	28	11	19	22	12	19
15	4	19	12	27	15	17	15	2	13
16	4	2	18	2	11	5	12	4	9
17	9	18	8	11	4	7	13	6	4
18	17	5	19	6	12	12	17	5	11
19	19	7	15	6	11	13	12	14	19
20	20	14	27	12	17	18	22	9	18
TOTAL	308	321	473	288	202	285	430	210	280

(Source: Kirkpatrick, 2010)

RESULTS

1. Prevalent Pronunciation Errors/Features that Students Frequently Make when Speaking

Figure 1. Distribution of Pronunciation Errors / Features of the Respondents

The figure displays the frequency of errors made by the participants in each category. It is essential to note that the speeches have varying lengths, as each respondent can choose their own. However, the teacher ensured that they presented it within a strict one-minute time limit.

2. Exercises to Devise for Speech Correction

According to the aforementioned bar graph on Pronunciation Features, the authors can suggest particular speech correction exercises aimed at addressing the most significant pronunciation difficulties. The predominant features are monophthongization, absence of reduced vowels, dental fricatives, and vowel merging, which should be prioritized. The following is a categorization of corrective exercises, namely: a. Monophthongization (Highest Frequency): Diphthong Drills; b. Lack of Reduced Vowels: Sentence Stress Patterns; c. Dental Fricatives (/θ/, /ð/): Tongue Twisters; d. Vowel Merging: Vowel Chart Mapping; e. Reduced Initial Aspiration: Video Feedback activity; f. Reduction of Consonant Clusters: Word Building Games; g. Bisyllabic Triphthongs: Mirror Drills; h. Heavy End-Stress: Poetry Reading; and, i. Stressed Pronouns: Role Playing.

DISCUSSION

Prevalent Pronunciation Errors/Features that Students Frequently Make when Speaking

It was presumed that each speaker spoke at nearly the same pace, as it was a topic of conversation regarding the optimal tempo at which a speech should be delivered, namely at a rate of 60 words every 30 seconds. When reducing consonant clusters, one of the traits observed is the omission of the final consonant sound in the word. The speakers appear to exclude the consonant, emphasizing the penultimate letter.

Some examples of this are given below (1-3):

- (1) It is a fac(t) that I have the ability... (speaker 2)
- (2) ...almos(t) one year ago... (speaker 4)
- (3) Firs(t), I wany to say to all of you... (speaker 19)

When it comes to dental fricative usage, there are many cases where the /θ/ is incorrect as it is always being substituted by /t/ or by /d/, as in (4-6):

- (4) ...not from (da) generosity of state but from (da) land of God. (speaker 6)
- (5) ...power which may be implemented by au(t)orities... (speaker 9)
- (6) ...(d)at is not true, not all (da) good (d)at we do is ever lost.

There are many cases where the vowel is pronounced short and changes its meaning, exemplified in (7-9):

- (7) It is altogether f(i)ttting and proper... (speaker 21)
- (8) Ind(l)d, one or after Japanese squadron... (speaker 1)
- (9) Who are witnesses of th(l)z nations... (speaker 13)

The group of features at the monophthongization of words includes examples such as *FACE and GOAT*. The main case of non-standard usage of this feature is failure to glide the vowel, a feature often found in L2 speech. The material in the present study has examples of this (10-12):

- (10) ...was suddenly and deliberately attacked by the emp(ar) of Japan (speaker 1)
- (11) President Clinton, disting(ish) guest and my fellow citizen... (speaker 5)
- (12) ...having the c(o)ld war end... (speaker 29)

One of the weakest features when it comes to the frequency of errors is the very minimal occurrence of failure to pronounce the reduced initial aspiration, as in (12-13):

- (12) ...we are and always will be, the United States of (A)merica (speaker 7)
- (13) Previous, to the official act of (v)llessedness... (speaker 10)

The sixth group here deals with the utterances of bisyllabic triphthongs in such a way that there is a short glide of the vowel that needs to be a little longer. Although used much more frequently in conversational discourse than in formal speeches, bisyllabic triphthongs are proven to be rare in spoken formal speeches. Correspondingly, there are few occurrences of this feature in the present study, as in (14-15):

- (14) ...we snatched (ar) victory (speaker 11)
(15) ... and seven years ago (ar) father brought forth (speaker 30)

Speakers in ELF contexts seem to have a lack of reduced vowels mainly by omitting the sound of it. e.g., *for the word 'officially', they tend to utter it as oflʃəll*. This type of usage is found mainly in the speech material in the present study as in (16-17):

- (16) My parents especi(ə)lly my father... (speaker 29)
(17) ...how hard it is (tu:) give life on... (speaker 28)
(18) I am glad (tu:) be a part of the peaceful transfer... (speaker 27)

The following typical pronunciation feature is a special case of deviance from standard spoken English, which is shared by Filipino usage: the stressed pronouns. They occur frequently in academic speech and are used by non-native English speakers to highlight important information. There are many examples of it in the material, especially in the speeches in (19-20):

- (19) First, I want to say to all of you... (speaker 24)
(20) ...for I have sworn before you... (speaker 20)
(21) ...by your verdict, he had demonstrated once again... (speaker 26)

Lastly, in the present study, heavy end-stress makes up a slightly smaller portion of the non-standard pronunciation features. Some examples of heavy end-stress are given in (21-23):

- (21) ...a story that will continue but an end we could not see. (speaker 5)
(22) We have met in that great battlefield of that war. (speaker 21)
(23) ...that is not true.

Essentially, it is evident that most of the participants made errors in combining long and short vowel sounds, as well as in using reduced vowels. The substitution of /i/ with /t/ was identified as problematic, as noted in Ambion's (2005) unpublished study, which highlighted fricatives as the most frequently produced consonants in the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA). While a few individuals have accurately positioned their articulatory organs during the production of fricatives, many respondents have been unable to do so correctly. The respondents effectively reduced consonant clusters to 12 monophthongized words and produced bisyllabic triphthongs with proficiency. The respondents perceive the smooth transition of words to be somewhat simpler, as was also observed during the debate about IPA. In this context, a sound is considered to have fixed articulation at both the beginning and end, without any upward or downward movement towards a new point of articulation. Monophthongs are distinguished from diphthongs by the absence of a change in vowel quality inside a single syllable. Hiatus, on the other hand, occurs when two vowels are adjacent to each other in separate syllables. This indicates that the fluent articulation of words during speech does not appear to be a difficulty for the speakers.

The findings suggest that intonation or word stress does not appear to be a significant issue for most participants. The data indicate that errors involving heavy end-stress and stressed pronouns are the least frequent, along with reduced initial aspiration.

Exercises to Devise for Speech Correction

a. *Monophthongization (Highest Frequency): Diphthong Drills*

Monophthongization refers to the simplification of diphthongs into single vowel sounds, such as pronouncing /aɪ/ as /a/. To correct this, Diphthong Drills are recommended. These involve focused practice on minimal pairs, such as “ride” vs. “rod” or “bite” vs. “bat.” Learners are guided to pronounce the glide of diphthongs clearly and consistently. Teachers may also use visual cues (e.g., hand movement) to show the transition between two vowel positions. Practicing with audio recordings and imitating native speaker pronunciation enhances learners’ awareness of vowel glides, promoting more natural-sounding speech. This data supports Chong's (2020) claim that spending 15 minutes, a few days a week, on whole-class activities and allocating around 10 minutes for differentiated small groups provides ample time for students requiring further practice to master phonological awareness.

b. *Lack of Reduced Vowels: Sentence Stress Patterns*

Reduced vowels, especially the schwa /ə/, are crucial for natural rhythm in English. Filipino speakers tend to pronounce all vowels fully, resulting in unnatural stress patterns. Sentence Stress Pattern exercises aim to teach learners the distinction between content and function words, helping them reduce the number of unstressed syllables in their speech. Students are trained to mark sentences with primary and secondary stress and to practice saying them aloud with appropriate reductions (e.g., “I want to go to the market” → /aɪ 'wʌnə gə tə ðə 'mɑ:kət/). These activities develop rhythm and prosody while helping learners sound more fluent and native-like.

c. *Dental Fricatives (/θ/, /ð/): Tongue Twisters*

Many learners substitute dental fricatives with /t/, /d/, or /s/, /z/ due to their unfamiliarity with /θ/ and /ð/. Tongue Twisters like “Thirty-three thousand feathers” or “The thief thought the throne was theirs” offer repeated practice with these sounds. These drills help learners isolate and exaggerate correct tongue placement, specifically between the teeth, for proper production. Teachers may combine these with visual demonstrations and tactile techniques, such as using a mirror or holding a finger near the mouth to feel airflow, reinforcing proper articulation.

d. *Vowel Merging: Vowel Chart Mapping*

Vowel merging occurs when distinct vowel sounds are pronounced identically, resulting in reduced clarity (e.g., merging /ɪ/ and /i:/). Vowel Chart Mapping trains learners to recognize and produce subtle vowel differences using IPA vowel diagrams. Students listen to minimal pairs (e.g., “bit” vs. “beat,” “ship” vs. “sheep”) and identify their positions on the chart. Visual mapping of tongue height and placement increases their phonetic awareness. Teachers can combine this with listening discrimination tasks and repetition drills to strengthen auditory and articulatory skills.

e. *Reduced Initial Aspiration: Video Feedback Activity*

In English, voiceless stops /p/, /t/, and /k/ are aspirated at the beginning of stressed syllables (e.g., “pin,” “top,” “cat”). Many learners omit this aspiration, resulting in flat or

voiced sounds. Video Feedback Activity involves learners recording themselves saying aspirated and unaspirated words, then comparing them to native models. Visual tools, such as placing a tissue in front of the mouth to observe aspiration (air puff), can be used during practice. Reviewing recordings helps learners self-correct and adjust their airflow and timing to include the appropriate aspiration.

f. Reduction of Consonant Clusters: Word Building Games

Learners often simplify consonant clusters by omitting one or more sounds (e.g., “tests” → “tes”). Word-building games encourage step-by-step construction of words with clusters. For example, building from “test” → “tests” → “tests’.” These games can be interactive, using flashcards or digital apps to match and pronounce words. Teachers can also guide learners to segment and blend cluster sounds slowly before speeding up. This structured repetition aids in mastering consonant sequencing and preserving word integrity.

g. Bisyllabic Triphthongs: Mirror Drills

Triphthongs like /aʊə/ or /aɪə/ can be challenging due to the rapid glide across three vowel sounds. Learners often simplify or omit transitions. Mirror Drills involve learners observing their mouth movements while producing triphthongs in bisyllabic words (e.g., “fire,” “power,” “layer”). Teachers guide them to exaggerate and slow down the glides. Watching mouth shapes ensures full articulation of all three sounds. This visual and kinesthetic feedback loop builds confidence and fluency in handling complex vowel structures.

h. Heavy End-Stress: Poetry Reading

Learners sometimes incorrectly stress the final syllable of sentences or words, which can disrupt the natural rhythm of speech. Poetry Reading helps internalize English intonation patterns through rhythm and meter. Reading aloud from rhythmic texts allows learners to practice natural stress and pitch variation. Teachers can use poems with strong iambic or trochaic meter to emphasize correct stress positioning. This activity promotes both expressive reading and rhythmic accuracy, reinforcing native-like cadence.

i. Stressed Pronouns: Role Playing

Overstressing pronouns (e.g., “I told YOU I did it”) disrupts natural English prosody. Role-playing helps learners use pronouns in context, with a focus on natural sentence stress. Through dialogues, learners act out everyday scenarios, emphasizing content words while reducing function words, such as pronouns and articles. This fosters a realistic and communicative environment where prosody becomes intuitive. Teachers may record and replay dialogues to highlight stress errors and reinforce corrections.

Each of these exercises is tailored to address a specific phonological challenge. It is paramount to making them highly effective in addressing the real-world speech patterns of learners, particularly in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) context, such as the Philippines, and carrying them effectively not only fosters sound-based language awareness but also critical self-regulated learning. This body of data aligns with Savvas

Learning Company LLC's (2025) claim that Phonological awareness is an essential skill, without which students cannot become strong, independent readers.

Conclusions

It is noteworthy that despite the relatively frequent occurrence of non-standard pronunciations, there is minimal communication breakdown due to the comprehensibility of English usage among the participants in the speech classroom. The results indicate a distinct inclination among students to minimize errors and prioritize functionality, regardless of traditional form. The sole factor that appears to result in communication breakdown is the unconventional combination of long and short vowel sounds, as well as the absence of reduced vowels, which is to be expected among Filipino English speakers. Nevertheless, noticeable issues, such as the emphasis on pronouns and the strong stress at the end of sentences, have already signaled a lack of focus, which may impede effective communication. It is essential to consider that this study has examined spoken English and explicit communication breakdown. The challenges may be concealed as this is a written speech, encompassing areas that are not audible, such as the unspoken or unspeakable aspects that speakers choose to omit or are unable to express.

This study also inferred the benefits of employing phonetic transcription to acquire accurate pronunciation, particularly in educational settings where English is the primary language of instruction and an official language. This is particularly relevant in countries like the Philippines, which can be characterized as semi-English-speaking. Upon careful evaluation, the benefits of learning phonetics in class are deemed valuable, prompting teachers to promote it to their students actively. Acquiring knowledge of phonetics will also afford learners the chance to engage with English, particularly as a widely used global language, for extended periods. This study has only focused on classroom-based phonetic instruction. However, the benefits identified in this study appear to apply to students from diverse dialect backgrounds.

Recommendations

Drawing from the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Explore and consider the inclusion of phonetics education in schools where English is not the primary language of instruction
2. Further empirical or experimental inquiry is needed.
3. Adopt a practical approach for speech teaching tailored to the needs of the students.
4. Devise an effective and appropriate material for speech teaching and evaluation.
5. Upgrade teachers' skills and methodologies in teaching speech.
6. It is recommended that future studies delve deeper into this study.
7. Incorporate multimedia tools and interactive technology (e.g., speech analysis applications, video modeling, pronunciation games) to enhance the engagement and data-driven nature of pronunciation instruction.

8. Create assessment rubrics centered on pronunciation that correspond to communicative competence, rather than native-like modeling, thereby more accurately representing students' practical application of English.
9. Encourage cooperation among language teachers and curriculum designers to create a unified and culturally attuned speech instruction program.
10. Foster learner autonomy in pronunciation practice by supplying self-assessment resources, including phonetic transcription manuals.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study examined how acoustic phonetics is used and understood in Philippine classrooms. While it offers a unique perspective, the researchers wish to make it clear that this paper does not intend to replicate or claim credit for similar studies that preceded it. All ideas and sources that informed this work have been appropriately cited and acknowledged. If any part of this paper is found to resemble another work too closely, the researchers welcome feedback, suggestions, or revisions to ensure the study adheres to the ethical standards of scholarly writing.

Acknowledgments

The researchers owe their deepest gratitude to their families, participants, and friends for the care, support, and inspiration they provided in completing this paper.

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